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To cite this article: Aarne Pohjonen *et al* 2025 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* **1335** 012028

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On the effect of solidification induced segregation on austenite formation and grain growth during re-heating of a forged steel part

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Abstract. We present initial results from a cellular automata (CA) model, which has been constructed to incorporate the effect of elemental segregation to the austenite nucleation and growth as well as grain growth during re-heating of a forged large scale steel object. The model has been constructed on the notion that there is position dependent variation in austenite grain structure of a quenched sample, which was obtained from re-heated forged object. The variation is thought to be a result of elemental segregation that has occurred during casting. The parameters of the previously developed CA model are adjusted for both alloy rich and alloy poor regions to mimic the experimentally observed grain structure.

1 Introduction

Medium carbon steels, suitably alloyed with elements like Cr, Mo, Ni and V, are suitable candidates for applications in powerplants, as they offer excellent combinations of strength and ductility along with excellent creep properties in optimized heat treated condition [1, 2]. The selection of alloy chemistry plays a vital role in the design and processing of these steels. For instance, 30CrMoNiV5-11 (typical composition range 0.3 C, 0.1-0.2 Si, 0.6-0.7 Mn, 1.3-1.4 Cr, 1.05 Mo, 0.6-0.7 Ni, 0.25-0.30 V wt%) [3] is one such grade that is used in the large shafts [4].

It is crucial that the prior austenite grain size is controlled at various austenitizing temperatures and holding times, including consideration of the influence of various heating rates from low to very low heating rates, thus simulating actual industrial heat treatment practice. For imparting optimized mechanical properties in a steel with least variation, it is important to control the transformed microstructure of the steel, which in turn depends on controlling the prior austenite grain size formed during the initial heating process, which needs to be uniformly fine [5, 6]. The prior austenite grain structure and size formed during austenitization treatment depends on its heating parameters, which in turn influence the final phase states in the steel and its mechanical properties [7]. This is because during subsequent cooling, the austenite grain boundaries act as the nucleation sites for different phases such as ferrite, pearlite, bainite, and martensite depending on the steel composition. Also, the hardenability of the steel is affected by the size of the individual prior austenite grains [8]. Hence, a fine prior austenite grain size results in an increased number of nucleation sites that enable a relatively fine grain size of the transformed phase, thus enhancing the mechanical properties of the steel [7]. On the contrary, if the austenitization parameters (heating path, austenitization temperature and hold time) lead to a significant variation in the grain size in the matrix resulting in a mixture of appreciably fine and coarse grains, it may result in the formation of correspondingly different phases during subsequent cooling. This can lead to an inhomogeneously

transformed microstructure in the final product, thus impacting its mechanical properties adversely, particularly the impact and fracture toughness properties [9, 10].

Hence, development of a suitable model, such as cellular automata (CA) model, encompassing nucleation and growth of austenite grains at different heating rates and subsequent holding in the austenitic regime at a given temperature and time [11] is inevitably necessary to be able to predict the austenite grain size distribution.

Although the chemical composition of the steel favors uniformity of elemental distribution throughout the matrix, the solidification process during the casting of the ingot, however, may actually result in extensive macrosegregation of the alloying elements, especially in large castings meant for industrial production [12] in the lengthscales of centimeter to meter. These castings are influenced by dendritic solidification which results in trapping of solute-rich liquid between the dendritic arms. These interdendritic regions later solidify into solute-rich regions [13, 14], a phenomena which is called microsegregation. Also, in the intermediate lengthscales between micro- and macrosegregation, mesosegregation can take place [15]. During subsequent hot working operations, not only the ingot is deformed into desired shapes through intensive plastic working, but also the coarse-grained dendritic structures are broken down to enable metallurgical restoration of structures leading to grain refinement and at least partial elimination of segregation bands [16]. However, alloy-rich, segregation-induced bands are often observed in these highly-alloyed steels and can significantly influence the local restoration, grain growth and phase transformation behaviours depending on the thermal/thermomechanical processing history [17]. [12]

Numerical modeling provides important insights on the microstructure development at different stages of thermomechanical processing of steels. For example, austenite formation during heating has been modeled using cellular automata [18, 11] and phase field methods [19]. Grain growth phenomena has been modeled using cellular automata [20, 11], level-set and vertex [21] methods; and austenite decomposition to ferritic phases has been modeled using phase field [22], level-set [23, 24] and cellular automata methods [25, 26, 27].

In the current study, we focus on the implementation of the segregation effects on a previously developed cellular automata (CA) model describing austenite formation and grain growth during heating [11]. The benefits of cellular automata model are: 1. Numerical efficiency due to relative simple formulation which allows simulations of large systems, 2. relatively easy implementation, 3. the capability of simulating the temperature and position dependent nucleation and growth rates and austenite grain growth to obtain position dependent grain size distribution. The drawbacks are that it is more difficult to incorporate physical phenomena such as diffusion and partitioning and elastic/plastic behavior to the model than e.g. in phase field or level-set models, which are based on solution of partial differential equations. The modification of the previous model [11] now allows to account for the segregation effects by considering the local variation in the model parameters as function of position.

2 Theory

The cellular automata model for including nucleation and growth of the austenite regions during heating and holding were described in the previous study [11]. In the current study, we include the effects of chemical segregation to the model parameters. For providing the full theory compactly, the description initially parallels closely to the one introduced in [11], but it is here augmented by including the segregation effects and their implementation to the model.

2.1 Nucleation

Based on the classical nucleation theory, the nucleation rate N_{het} can be described by the following equation [28] :

$$N_{\text{het}} = \omega C \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G_m}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

where R is the ideal gas constant, C the concentration of nucleation sites, ω the attempt frequency for the nucleation, ΔG_m the activation energy per atom for atomic migration between the austenitic and ferritic regions and ΔG^* the energy barrier for nucleation of austenite from ferrite. ΔG^* is strongly dependent on the temperature relative to the equilibrium temperature T_{eq} (i.e. the overheating). The local chemical composition affects the ΔG^* as well as the equilibrium temperature.

As described in [11], $\omega C \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT}\right)$ in Eq. (1) is replaced with the phenomenological expression $A(T - T_{\text{eq}})^a \left(1 - \frac{\chi}{\chi_{\text{max}}(T)}\right)^b$, where χ is the transformed austenite fraction, $\chi_{\text{max}}(T)$ is the temperature

dependent maximum austenite fraction. In the current study we applied Thermocalc [29] to calculate the temperature dependent maximum austenite fraction and equilibrium temperatures. The factor $\left(1 - \frac{\chi}{\chi_{\max}(T)}\right)^b$ limits the austenite transformation to the maximum fraction that can be transformed at the temperature T . As the temperature increases above the equilibrium temperature, the driving force increases rapidly, described by the approximating power law function. The parameters A , a and b are kinetic fitting parameters that can be obtained by fitting the model to experimental data. The parameters a and A are commonly used to represent the temperature dependence of the driving force, see e.g. [30]. Parameter b enables taking account nucleation rate dependence on the transformed fraction at temperature T , which can be non-linear.

$$N_{\text{het}} = A(T - T_{\text{eq}})^a \left(1 - \frac{\chi}{\chi_{\max}(T)}\right)^b \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta G_m}{RT}\right) \quad (2)$$

2.2 Austenite to ferrite growth

Austenite growth with speed $v_{\gamma\alpha}$ to the surrounding ferrite matrix is considered as a thermally activated process using the Arrhenius type equation

$$v_{\gamma\alpha} = F \left(1 - \frac{\chi}{\chi_{\max}(T)}\right)^c \exp\left(-\frac{Q_G}{RT}\right) \quad (3)$$

where F is a constant pre-factor containing the attempt frequency and average atomic sites per unit length as well as the length of austenite interface progression due to one transformation event. The physically based parameter Q_G is the lumped overall activation barrier which can be used to describe the effective thermal activation of the phase boundary movement (see details in e.g. [24]).[11] Parameters F and c are phenomenological fitting parameters yielding similar functionality for growth as parameters A and b have to the nucleation model.

2.3 Austenite to austenite growth (austenite grain growth)

The speed of the interface between two neighbouring austenite grains v has been implemented based on [20] and is described by the equation (4)

$$v = \frac{H}{kT} \exp\left(-\frac{Q_b}{RT}\right) \kappa \quad (4)$$

where κ is the curvature, H and Q_b are parameters for fitting the thermally activated, curvature dependent interface mobility. [11] The linear dependence of interface movement on the grain boundary curvature is often used in this context [21, 20] and it leads to well know grain coarsening phenomena.

2.4 Effect of segregation to austenite formation and grain growth

The segregation phenomena can affect all of the model parameters. However, it can be noted that the change in the activation energy values ΔG^* (represented by A and a), ΔG_m , ΔQ_G and Q_b have relatively much larger effect to the evolution of the phase regions compared to the pre-exponential factors F and H . The effect of variation in composition on the temperature dependent equilibrium temperatures can be obtained from thermodynamic databases. The segregation can also affect the thermodynamic driving force for nucleation and growth and its dependence on the transformed fraction, which are described by parameters a , b and c .

If the model has large number of fitting parameters, it can become difficult to find a unique combination of parameters that best fits the model. For this reason, it is suggested, at least initially, to focus on the effect of those parameters that have the most significant effect and can be obtained relatively easily. Initially, the model can be assumed to have linear dependence on transformed fraction relative to the maximum transformed fraction, setting $b = c = 1$. Since the change in activation energies ΔG^* (represented by parameters A and a), ΔG_m , ΔQ_G and ΔQ_b have large effect on the transformation behaviour, it is suggested that their variation due to the segregation effect is taken into account. Since the change in pre-exponential factors F and H has relatively much less effect in the transformation behavior, it is suggested, in the first instance, to fit constant values for these parameters.

2.4.1 Dendrite arm spacings during solidification The primary and secondary dendrite arm spacings (PDAS and SDAS) can be calculated with equation of the form of equation (5) as described in [31, 32]

$$d = \frac{A}{R^n} \quad (5)$$

where d is the arm spacing, R is the cooling rate during solidification in $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$. A and n are constants. To obtain an order of magnitude estimate for the dendrite arm spacings, the Inter Dendritic Solidification (IDS) software [33] was used to calculate the primary and secondary arm spacings for different cooling rates and linear fit was performed to $(\log(d), \log(\text{CR}))$ data, from which the values $A_{\text{PDAS}} = \exp(5.1102)$, $n_{\text{PDAS}} = 0.3507$; $A_{\text{SDAS}} = \exp(4.5494)$ and $n_{\text{SDAS}} = 0.3023$ were obtained for the currently investigated steel.

3 Experimental observations of segregation phenomena

The 30CrMoNiV5-11 steel was initially cast as 1 meter diameter and after forging it was roughly 4 m long. After forging the part has undergone several thermal processing steps, which are not discussed in current article in more detail, since the aim of this study is to focus on the implementation of the segregation effects to the cellular automata model.

A Gleeble thermomechanical simulator was used to conduct thermomechanical test schedule on a test sample. A sample of dimension ϕ 6 mm x 36 mm height, taken from the lower section of the turbine rotor shaft, obtained after the preliminary heat treatment (normalized and tempered conditions), was reheated to 950 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a heating rate of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{sec}$. The soaking time of the sample at the austenitization temperature was 30 minutes to obtain a comparable austenite grain size that of the industrial condition. After this the sample was cooled at a cooling rate of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{sec}$ to room temperature. To reveal the prior austenite grains, the sample was ground, polished and etched using Bechet-Beaujard (BB) [34] etchant as shown in Fig. 1(a). From the figure, it was clearly observed that there are differences in the austenite grain size from one area to another due to segregation induced during the casting process. The tentative explanation for this is that due to the effect of microsegregation in the steel, the austenite grain size was finer in the alloy-rich (interdendritic) region whereas the austenite grain size was coarser in the alloy-lean (dendritic) regions. Additionally, a JEOL JXA-8530FPlus FE EPMA (electron probe microanalyzer) equipment was utilized to observe the alloy rich (AR) and alloy poor (AP) regions in more detail, as shown in Fig. 1(b). It is quite clear that there is a difference in the concentration of alloying element Mo in different regions of the microstructure confirming the variation of prior austenite grain size.

Figure 1: (a) Optical microstructure showing prior austenite grains (using Bechet-Beaujard (BB) etchant) after cooling the steel specimen at a cooling rate of 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$, observed using confocal laser scanning microscope, showing alloy-rich (AR) and alloy-poor (AP) regions, and (b) EPMA analysis showing the variation of %Mo content in the alloy-rich (AR) and alloy-poor (AP) region (different location than a)

The dendrite arm spacings calculated using Eq. (5) for cooling rates between 0.001 °C/s and 0.01 °C/s yield estimates for SDAS = 381...763 μm and PDAS = 833...1868 μm . Since the microstructure has been compressed due to forging, it can be expected that the initial SDAS regions could be flattened to $\sim 10\text{-}30\%$ of the value, which would be from (38...76) to (114...229) μm , indicating a similar order of magnitude to the interval between observed segregation regions.

4 Numerical test case for simulating segregation effects

The current study focuses on the initial implementation of the segregation effects to the austenite formation and grain growth by implementing position dependence on the model parameters. The simulation results demonstrate this implementation, which can be in future parameterized by fitting to experimental results. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in the simulations. It is noted that this causes sharp transition on the upper part, which is not realistic and should be neglected. However, the aim of the current demonstration is to show the effect of the smooth variation in the middle of the simulation cell. The applied model parameters are shown in Tables 1,2 and 3.

Parameter	Explanation	Value
ΔG_m	Activation energy	170 kJ/mol
T_{A1}	A_1 transition temperature	719.5 °C
T_{A3}	A_3 transition temperature	806.4 °C
A	Kinetic fitting parameter	0.1 1/(°Cs)
a	Kinetic fitting parameter	1
b	Kinetic fitting parameter	1

Table 1: Nucleation parameters

Parameter	Explanation	Value
F	Growth pre-factor	0.00025 m/s
Q_G	Activation energy for growth	150 kJ/mol
c	Kinetic fitting parameter	1

Table 2: Austenite to ferrite growth parameters

Parameter	Explanation	Value
H	Pre-factor for grain growth	2.59362×10^{-9} (eV m)/(K s)
Q_b	Activation energy for grain growth	80.966 kJ/mol

Table 3: Austenite grain growth parameters

The effect of segregation region has been included as a multiplicative factor that affects activation energy of nucleation and growth, decreasing phase transformation and grain growth rates. Since the segregation also affects the equilibrium temperature, we demonstrate the implementation by setting the local equilibrium temperature as $T_{\text{eq}} = T_{\text{eq}0} + 300(s - 1)$, where $T_{\text{eq}0}$ corresponds to the alloy poor region and s is the segregation factor. For this article, an example segregation region has been generated, see right bottom corner of Fig. 2. The segregated alloy rich region is initialized on the top half the viewing window, so the bottom half corresponds to the alloy poor region. There is a smooth transition between the alloy rich and alloy poor regions.

With the segregation region factor, the growth rate retarding effect is controlled by the equilibrium transformation temperatures and other model parameters. To demonstrate this effect, example simulations were run using (1) no segregation region (segregation factor = 1 everywhere) and (2) multiplicative segregation region factor varying from 1 to 1.2, affecting the transformation temperatures and activation energies ΔG_m , Q_G and Q_b .

Simulation starting temperature was 720 °C, which was heated with heating rate 25 °C/s up to 950 °C, then held for a total of 120 seconds. The results are shown in Fig 2. The different colors are used

to separate grain instances from each other. As can be seen, the area with the segregation region has severely retarded phase transformation from ferrite to austenite and the subsequent grain growth. The actual change in the parameter values will be in future calibrated using thermodynamic databases and softwares as well using experimental data. Due to simplicity and rapid calculation time, the model has relatively few parameters, and for given steel they can be found by systematically running simulations and comparing the observed grain size distributions to experimental data. A suitable experimental campaign could consist of interrupted heating tests to different temperatures with subsequent quenching to see the austenite structure that has formed during the heating. This will allow for calibrating the kinetic parameters of the model. The equilibrium A_1 and A_3 temperatures as well as the temperature dependent maximum austenite fraction can be obtained from thermodynamic database, such as Thermocalc.

Figure 2: Effect of segregation region to the activation energy factor and equilibrium temperature on the austenitization and grain growth phenomena in the implemented numerical model.

5 Conclusions

Variation of austenite grain structure was observed in 30CrMoNiV5-11 type steel. Since elemental analysis has indicated that the observed variation is caused by segregation of elements, segregation effects were introduced to the previously implemented cellular automata model, which describes the austenite formation and grain growth during heating. We present demonstration of the implemented position dependent variation in austenite formation and grain growth parameters by numerical test case. In the future studies we will aim to fit the model using thermodynamic softwares and to experimentally observed austenite grain structure that will be obtained from interrupted heating tests, as well as grain growth studies.

6 Acknowledgments

Guidance in using IDS software from Dr. Tuomas Alatarvas is gratefully acknowledged. The Reinosa Forging and Castings is acknowledged for providing the material. Modeling results from Fraunhofer IWM on accumulated plastic strain were used in comparing the compression of microstructure of as cast material. Funding from the AID4GREENEST project is acknowledged: This research has received funding from the European Commission under the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 101091912). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

7 Author contributions

A. P. theory, O. S. numerical model implementation, R. B. experiments and initial observations of segregation effects, M. S. conceptualization and topic selection, supervision of experimental work.

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